

Orbital determination with Gauss's method

Milagros Tamara Giraldo

*Physics Photonics and Optical Engineering Department
Bridgewater State University
Bridgewater, United States
mtamaragiraldo@student.bridgew.edu*

Matthew Payne

*Solar, Stellar & Planetary Sciences
Center for Astrophysics — Harvard & Smithsonian
Cambridge, United States
mpayne@cfa.harvard.edu*

Federica Spoto

*Solar, Stellar & Planetary Sciences
Center for Astrophysics — Harvard & Smithsonian
Cambridge, United States
federica.spoto@cfa.harvard.edu*

Abstract—Accurately predicting the orbital trajectory of celestial objects is essential for precise spacecraft navigation, planning planetary missions, avoiding potential collisions with space debris, and studying the long-term stability of planetary systems. Gauss's method for orbital determination provides a way to predict the path of a celestial body accurately using a small number of observations. This project focuses on understanding the mathematical and physical foundations of Gauss's method. Based on this understanding we then develop a fast, user-friendly implementation of Gauss's method in Python that incorporates modern coding practices and code efficiency.

This Python implementation can be used to gain a deeper understanding of Gauss's method. Running multiple sets of data within a few seconds allows us to easily generate statistics and compare results, providing the opportunity to “dissect” Gauss's method into its different components to analyze the results. We can look for the solution to more complex questions such as: When does the method produce the most accurate results? When does it not produce results? How much does the interval between observations affect the results? How does the scale of the measurement error affect the results? This implementation is not only a tool for applying Gauss's method, but also for studying it in greater depth.

Index Terms—Orbital Determination, Asteroids, Python

I. INTRODUCTION

In early 1801, astronomers observed a celestial object named Ceres, which they soon lost because the light from the object became overwhelmed by the glare from the Sun. At the time, a young mathematician named Carl Friedrich Gauss developed a method that allowed astronomers to recover the object by predicting where Ceres was going to reappear many months later when it had moved far enough away from the Sun to become visible [1]. Gauss would later become one of the most recognized figures not only in astronomy but also in mathematics and physics, due to his many contributions, including the least squares method, the Gaussian distribution, Gauss's law of electrodynamics, and many others that are still widely used and applied today.

Bridgewater State University

The mathematical method that he introduced to predict Ceres' path is now referred to as “Gauss's method for orbital determination”. Using as few as three observations of an asteroid, Gauss's method can produce accurate orbital estimates that can predict where an asteroid will reappear. This is not an easy task to achieve because the orbital path of an asteroid follows an elliptical shape, as shown in Fig. V. This orbit can be affected by the surrounding environment, specifically by the body of masses that are near it, making predictions of the trajectory even more difficult. The achievement of successfully predicting the trajectory of an asteroid using Gauss's method marked an important breakthrough in the field of celestial mechanics and the field of ‘orbital determination’: the science of predicting or reconstructing the paths of celestial bodies. As he developed this method, he also invented the least-squares method to make the prediction more accurate. Gauss officially published the Gauss's method in 1809 in his book *Theoria Motus Corporum Coelestium* [1].

Today, orbital determination is crucial for a number of reasons. It allows us to assess potential dangers from incoming asteroids or space debris, helps ensure satellite orbits remain clear, and is essential for space exploration missions, where knowing the precise positions of celestial bodies is critical for navigation and successful rocket launches.

Fig. 1. Elliptical orbit of an asteroid with the Sun at one focus of the ellipse.

This project focuses on understanding Gauss's method and modernizing an existing code implementation of it. Originally,

we worked with code from the Fortran-based *OrbFit* software package. Due to Fortran being less widely used today, we translated and extended the implementation of the code in Python.

Python offers broader accessibility, compatibility with other code-bases, and the ability to apply modern programming practices such as modular design, unit testing, and scalable development, to this mathematical method. In this paper, we explore both the mathematical foundations of Gauss’s method and its code implementation. In Section II, we will present a detailed examination of the mathematical formulation of Gauss’s method, including a step-by-step explanation of how the underlying mathematics operates.

In Section III, we focus on the Python implementation of Gauss’s method. We begin by introducing the original Fortran implementation, outlining its main structure and contrasting its features with those of Python. We then discuss how these differences were considered during the direct translation process, describing in detail how the transition between the two programming languages was achieved. Next, we build upon the mathematical foundations of Gauss’s method and our translated Python version to develop an improved, fully Python based implementation. This section also explores the enhancements introduced in the new code, including the reasoning behind specific design choices and the impact of adopting modern programming practices. In section IV, we address the challenges and difficulties we encounter throughout this research project. Lastly, in Section V we present our conclusions and outline potential future directions for this work, including opportunities for further optimization and application in celestial mechanics.

II. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

In this section we review the mathematical foundations of Gauss’s method described in [3], [4] and [2].

We start by understanding our *inputs* (our known, measured quantities): we are provided with three observations of the asteroid in the form of right ascension (RA) and declination (DEC). These are angular coordinates that describe the direction in the sky where the asteroid was observed. From these two angles, we can construct a three-dimensional unit vector that points in the direction of the asteroid at each observation time. This unit vector will be denoted as $\hat{\rho}_i$, taken at times, t_i , where the index $i \in [1, 2, 3]$.

Fig. 2 helps visualize the geometric relationship among the three observations. Where we illustrate the vector $\vec{\rho}_i$, which represents both the direction of the observation $\hat{\rho}_i$ and the distance of the asteroid from the respective observatory $|\rho_i|$. We emphasize that while the *directions*, $\hat{\rho}_i$, are known, the *distances*, $|\rho_i|$, are not.

Gauss’s method proceeds under the following assumptions:

- The observer is located at known heliocentric position vectors $\vec{R}_1, \vec{R}_2, \vec{R}_3$.
- The observed line-of-sight unit vectors (from the observer to the asteroid) $\hat{\rho}_1, \hat{\rho}_2, \hat{\rho}_3$ are known.

- The asteroid lies in a Keplerian orbit; and thus its three heliocentric radius vectors $\vec{r}_1, \vec{r}_2, \vec{r}_3$ at the observed positions are *coplanar*.

Fig. 2. Asteroid observations from 3 different observatories, where the blue dots represent the asteroid position at the three different times, which we write as vectors $\vec{\rho}_i = |\rho_i|\hat{\rho}_i$.

Given the above, we want to determine the heliocentric orbit of the asteroid at time t_2 .

We express the heliocentric position of the asteroid at each time as:

$$\vec{r}_i = \vec{R}_i + \rho_i \hat{\rho}_i \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, 3. \quad (1)$$

Fig. 3. Vector addition between the position vector of the asteroid from the observatory $\vec{\rho}_i$ and the observatory’s position vector relative to the sun’s center \vec{R}_i , results in the asteroid’s position vector, relative to the sun’s center \vec{r}_i .

From each observation, we obtain the heliocentric position vector of the asteroid, \vec{r}_i . Because all observations correspond to the same object and lie on the same orbital plane, the position vectors are coplanar. Therefore, we can assume linear dependence between the \vec{r}_i such that:

$$c_1 \vec{r}_1 + c_2 \vec{r}_2 + c_3 \vec{r}_3 = 0 \quad (2)$$

Fig. 4. Heliocentric position vectors of the asteroid, \vec{r}_i , with respect to the center of the sun, illustrating the coplanar nature of the vectors and their linear dependence.

We can then solve for the coefficients c_1 and c_3 by considering the non-trivial solution of the linear dependence

equation and setting $c_2 = -1$. Using vector cross products, the coefficients can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} c_1 &= \frac{(\vec{r}_2 \times \vec{r}_3)}{(\vec{r}_1 \times \vec{r}_3)}, \\ c_3 &= \frac{(\vec{r}_1 \times \vec{r}_2)}{(\vec{r}_1 \times \vec{r}_3)}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Because the three position vectors correspond to observations of the same object moving along a Keplerian orbit, the relationship between them can be expressed through the f and g functions, which describe how the position and velocity of a body evolve over time under gravitational motion. Using these functions, we can write:

$$\vec{r}_1 = f_1 \vec{r}_2 + g_1 \vec{v}_2 \quad (4)$$

$$\vec{r}_3 = f_3 \vec{r}_2 + g_3 \vec{v}_2. \quad (5)$$

I.e. we have expressed the positions at times 1 and 3 in terms of the position and velocity at time 2.

The f and g functions are defined as series expansions containing an infinite number of terms. However, to apply Gauss's method and obtain a practical solution, we use the second-order approximation, which is expressed as [3]:

$$\begin{aligned} f_i &= 1 - \frac{\sigma}{2}(\Delta t_i)^2, \\ g_i &= \Delta t_i - \frac{\sigma}{6}(\Delta t_i)^3, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $\sigma = \frac{\mu}{r_2^3}$ and $\mu = \text{Gravitational parameter}$

We then rewrite (3), by expressing \vec{r}_1 and \vec{r}_3 in terms of the f and g functions:

$$c_1 = \frac{g_3}{f_1 g_3 - f_3 g_1}, \quad c_3 = \frac{-g_1}{f_1 g_3 - f_3 g_1}. \quad (7)$$

Then we use our definitions of the f and g function presented on (6) to write c_1 and c_3 as:

$$c_1 = \underbrace{\frac{\Delta t_3}{\Delta t_3 - \Delta t_1}}_{a_1} + \underbrace{\frac{\Delta t_3 ((\Delta t_3 - \Delta t_1)^2 - (\Delta t_3)^2)}{6(\Delta t_3 - \Delta t_1)}}_{b_1} \sigma \quad (8)$$

$$c_1 = a_1 + b_1 \sigma$$

And in a similar manner:

$$c_3 = \underbrace{\frac{-\Delta t_1}{\Delta t_3 - \Delta t_1}}_{a_3} + \underbrace{\frac{-\Delta t_1 ((\Delta t_3 - \Delta t_1)^2 - (\Delta t_1)^2)}{6(\Delta t_3 - \Delta t_1)}}_{b_3} \sigma \quad (9)$$

$$c_3 = a_3 + b_3 \sigma$$

We can construct a system of equations using (1), taking into account the linear dependence described in (2) and using the scalar product. The resulting system of equations is represented as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\rho}_1 & \hat{\rho}_2 & \hat{\rho}_3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} c_1 \rho_1 \\ c_2 \rho_2 \\ c_3 \rho_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{R}_1 & \vec{R}_2 & \vec{R}_3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} -c_1 \\ -c_2 \\ -c_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

Next, we move the unit vector of ρ , which represents the data we gather from our three observations, to the left side of the equation by taking its inverse.

$$\begin{bmatrix} c_1 \rho_1 \\ c_2 \rho_2 \\ c_3 \rho_3 \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\rho}_1 & \hat{\rho}_2 & \hat{\rho}_3 \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \vec{R}_1 & \vec{R}_2 & \vec{R}_3 \end{bmatrix}}_B \begin{bmatrix} -c_1 \\ -c_2 \\ -c_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

The resulting matrix, from the matrix product between the inverse of the ρ unit vector and the position of the observatory \vec{R} is labeled as the B matrix. Using this matrix and our definitions for $c_2 = -1$, and c_1 & c_3 from (8) and (9), we can solve for the magnitude of the second observation $|\hat{\rho}_2|$, with the following equation:

$$|\rho_2| = \underbrace{B_{21}a_1 - B_{22} + B_{23}a_3}_{d_1} + \underbrace{(B_{21}b_1 + B_{23}b_3)}_{d_2} \sigma \quad (11)$$

$$|\rho_2| = d_1 + d_2 \sigma$$

With this we can go back to our vector addition in (1), and calculate the magnitude of \vec{r}_i , following this formula:

$$\|\vec{r}_i\| = \|\vec{\rho}_i + \vec{R}_i\| = \sqrt{\|\rho_i\|^2 + \|\vec{R}_i\|^2 + 2\|\rho_i\|\hat{\rho}_i \cdot \vec{R}_i} \quad (12)$$

This means that we now know both the magnitude and direction of the second observation, $\hat{\rho}_2$, hence we can solve for the asteroid's position vector at time $t = 2$. To determine this position vector, we substitute our previous result from (11) and obtain the following expression:

$$\begin{aligned} r_2^8 &= \left(d_1^2 + \|\vec{R}_2\|^2 + 2d_1\hat{\rho}_2 \cdot \vec{R}_2 \right) r_2^6 + \\ &2(d_1 d_2 + d_2 \hat{\rho}_2 \cdot \vec{R}_2) r_2^3 \mu + d_2^2 \mu^2 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

The result of this derivation in Eqn. (13) is an 8th degree polynomial that solves for the asteroid's distance at the time of the second observation, r_2 . Once we determine the value of r_2 we can calculate the corresponding position vectors at the first and third observations \vec{r}_1 and \vec{r}_3 . These position vectors then allow us to compute the asteroid's velocity enabling us to fully predict the asteroid's path.

Because this is an eighth-degree polynomial, the equation can yield multiple mathematical roots. However, not all of the roots correspond to physically meaningful solutions. In practice, up to three real, positive roots can be valid for r_2 while the remaining may be imaginary or negative, which are not possible solutions for this problem.

The formulation of Gauss's method reveals several important constraints that arise throughout the mathematical derivation, including:

- Gauss's method provides an estimate that carries inherent uncertainties. These uncertainties originate from the core of the method itself, particularly due to the approximations applied to the f - and g -functions to make the equations more computationally tractable.
- The accuracy and success of this method depends heavily on the geometry and quality of the observations. Inaccuracies in the observational data directly affect the reliability

of the computed roots and, consequently, the derived orbital parameters.

- Another critical factor influencing the results is the time interval between observations. Gauss’s method performs best when observations are closely spaced in time but not overlapping. If the intervals are too close or coincide, numerical complications can arise; specifically, issues in computing the B matrix, which would make it impossible to form the eighth-degree polynomial and, therefore, to solve Gauss’s method altogether.

Despite these constraints, Gauss’s method remains one of the most effective techniques for preliminary orbit determination. Modern adaptations and variations of the method continue to address these challenges, improving its robustness and accuracy in contemporary astronomical applications [3].

III. PYTHON IMPLEMENTATION

To begin developing the computational portion of this project, we started by examining a Fortran implementation of Gauss’s method that had previously been developed within the *OrbFit* software package, created by accredited scientists in the field of astrophysics. We accessed asteroid data through the *Minor Planet Center* to supply as input to the code.

I first familiarized myself with how the Fortran program operated, understanding its input requirements, behavior, and data structure. Once I was comfortable running the program, I began exploring the source code directly. For several days, I carefully studied the raw Fortran file, adding notes and annotations to understand the purpose of each section, variable, and operation. This process was particularly challenging, as I had no prior experience with Fortran syntax and conventions. Nonetheless, this close engagement with the source code proved invaluable for developing my own code later on. I began with making small modifications to the code, such as by displaying a text message on the terminal. Being able to perform these modifications, became essential later on for debugging the Python implementation and comparing the Fortran operation results to the Python operation results.

After achieving a solid grasp of the Fortran logic, I began creating a line-by-line Python translation. Each variable, parameter, and subroutine was replicated exactly as it appeared in the Fortran version, maintaining consistent naming and value assignments, making only necessary changes throughout the way, such as instead of defining a variable as a Fortran Double data type, on the python translation the variable would be defined as a Python float data type, due to Python not having an embedded double datatype.

While the Fortran code was largely written as a single monolithic subroutine, the translated Python version was modularized from the beginning as display in Fig. 5. This modular design allowed for easier debugging, testing, and readability. Each computational step, such as matrix inversion, vector normalization, or polynomial root solving, was implemented in a separate function, making it simpler to isolate and verify errors.

Fortran Implementation

```
tis2=tobs(2)
A and B vectors
tau1=rootgm*(tobs(1)-tis2) ! mu*t_12
tau3=rootgm*(tobs(3)-tis2) ! mu*t_32
tau13=tau3-tau1 ! mu*t_31
a(1)= tau3/tau13
a(2)=-1.d0
a(3)=-tau1/tau13
b(1)=a(1)*(tau13**2-tau3**2)/6.d0
b(2)=0.d0
b(3)=a(3)*(tau13**2-tau1**2)/6.d0
Coefficients of 8th degree equation for r2
```

Python Implementation

```
def get_tau_values(time_obs: list, rootgm: float = 1.7202098949957226E-002):
    """Provided with a set of three times of observations and mue square valu
    tau_1 = rootgm * (time_obs[0] - time_obs[1])
    tau_3 = rootgm * (time_obs[2] - time_obs[1])
    tau13 = tau_3 - tau_1
    return (tau13, tau_1, tau_3)

def make_a_b(tau13: float, tau1: float, tau3: float):
    """Provided three tau values (tau, tau_1, tau_3), calculated with the obser
    a_1 = tau3 / tau13
    b_1 = a_1 * (tau13**2 - tau3**2) / 6
    a_3 = -tau1 / tau13
    b_3 = a_3 * (tau13**2 - tau1**2) / 6
    return (a_1, b_1, a_3, b_3)
```

Fig. 5. This figure shows the Python implementation that is a direct translation to the Fortran code with the addition of being modularized

One of the main challenges in this process was learning how to correctly translate Fortran syntax and logic into Python. A few examples of syntax conversions between the two languages are shown in table I.

TABLE I
SYNTAX DIFFERENCES

Fortran Syntax	Python syntax
DO k=1,3	for k in range(3):
.EQ.	==
.LE.	<=
.GE.	>=
CALL solv8()	solv8()

This translation process also revealed differences in indexing conventions, looping behavior, and array handling. The goal of this first Python program was to produce a “sanity check”, allowing us to verify that a Python program that followed the same logic, step-by-step, as the Fortran code, would replicate the same numerical results as the Fortran routine.

This Python implementation that mirrors the Fortran structure exactly, becomes key to understanding that any discrepancies in output from our own Python implementation would arise from mathematical or unit-handling issues, not from Python’s computational capabilities. This Python direct translation of the code was able to produce accurate results that were precise up to the 12th decimal place with the Fortran results.

Once the direct Fortran-to-Python translation was complete and verified, we proceeded to develop a new Python implementation from scratch. Developing this code was not a simple translation of code from Fortran to Python, but a full interpretation of Gauss’s method that directly agrees-with, and is derived-from, the mathematical exposition in section II. This “second” Python version was designed to be cleaner, faster, and more modular while maintaining the same physical meaning and numerical results as the Fortran implementation.

In this enhanced implementation, all major calculations were expressed using NumPy array operations, which not only increased efficiency, but also made it possible to handle multiple sets of three observations simultaneously. The result was a system capable of performing Gauss’s Method on many datasets in parallel, something that would have been cumbersome to implement in the original Fortran code, a snippet of this code can be seen on Fig. 6.

```
def gauss_method(observation_times,p,R):
    inverse_p = mf.take_inverse_matrix(p)
    B_matrix = inverse_p@R
    delta_t1,delta_t3,delta_t= calculate_delta_t(t0,t1,t2)
    a1,b1,a3,b3 = calculate_a_and_b(delta_t1,delta_t3,delta_t)
    d_1,d_2,magnitude_R_2,pos_2_dot_p2= calculate_values_for_cs(a1,b1,a3,b3,R,p,B_matrix)
    c,c3,c6,c8= calculate_cs(d_1,d_2,magnitude_R_2,pos_2_dot_p2)
    roots = mf.eight_equation_four_coeff(c,c3,c6,c8)
```

Fig. 6. This figure is a snippet of the enhanced Python implementation. It includes familiar quantities from Section II, such as the B matrix on (10) and the a_1 and b_1 values from (8). The code is directly based on the mathematical derivation presented in Section II, where the variable p on the code corresponds to the unit vector $\hat{\rho}_i$.

A. Features of the Enhanced Python Implementation

Comprehensive Documentation:

Each function includes detailed doc-strings explaining its purpose, inputs, outputs, and underlying equations. A separate documentation file summarizes the entire workflow, allowing new users or researchers to easily understand the logic of the program and adapt it to their own data.

NumPy-based Vectorization:

All numerical operations are performed using vectorized NumPy functions, greatly improving computational performance and reducing memory overhead. This approach also allowed for a smooth transition between single- and multi-dataset processing.

Automated Testing and Validation:

Every function in the program is paired with at least one test function to verify correctness. These tests can be executed manually or automatically through GitHub Actions, ensuring continuous ongoing testing whenever the repository is updated. This framework made debugging faster and gave confidence that each code modification preserved expected behavior.

Modular and Accessible Design:

Following modern software engineering practices, the Python code was organized into small, self-contained modules. Each module performs a specific task (for example, computing position vectors, converting between coordinate

systems, or solving the eight degree polynomial). This modularity enhances code readability, simplifies debugging, and allows independent testing of each component.

The direct translation phase provided strong assurance that Python could faithfully reproduce Fortran’s results, while the enhanced version leveraged Python’s structure to make the method more efficient and maintainable.

Limitations: Despite the success in developing this enhanced implementation. The resulting roots from the Python enhanced code implementation agrees with the Fortran code implementation up to the 12th decimal place, as shown in table II. An error in the 12th decimal place of the position vector of the asteroid r_2 , corresponds to an uncertainty of approximately one meter in the computed orbital position. However, this precision discrepancy is believed to come from the rounding variations in the Python implementation, probably due to differences in how NumPy handles double precision compared to Fortran.

TABLE II
RESULT COMPARISON

r_2 from Fortran	r_2 from Python
0.98366052181486430	0.9836605218147869
1.0544796939362728	1.0544796939365233
1.2457493693119874	1.2457493693117867

IV. CHALLENGES

Throughout the development process, we encountered several key challenges, both in understanding the underlying mathematics and in implementing the code efficiently. One major difficulty was locating detailed, beginner-accessible sources explaining the mathematical foundations of Gauss’s method. Most available resources assumed prior knowledge, making it difficult to reconstruct the derivation from basic principles for Section II. Other key challenges emerged in Section III on the Python implementation, was maintaining unit consistency, which was essential to ensure that the numerical results were both logical and accurate. Determining whether computations were being performed in Cartesian or Keplerian coordinates, and whether the reference frame was equatorial or ecliptic, proved critical, as these choices had a significant impact on the numerical results. Nevertheless, the modular design of our code and consistent testing allowed us to efficiently identify and resolve discrepancies. Another challenge involved data type management within Python. It was necessary to understand how to process a single dataset containing three observations versus multiple datasets processed in bulk using NumPy arrays. Initially, we attempted to handle this using conditional loops that adjusted operations depending on input size. However, we later simplified this approach by adding an extra array dimension, allowing vectorized operations to handle all datasets easily, this approach is visible in Fig. 7. This greatly improved efficiency, readability, and debugging.

```

def gauss_method(observation_times,p,R):
    # size determines the amount of sets
    # that the program is working with
    size = int(len(size_tobs) / 3)
    # making R, and P numpy arrays and changing
    # any dimension of the provided parameters.
    p = np.array(p)
    R = np.array(R)
    # changing dimension of matrices
    if R.ndim > 3:
        R = np.reshape(R,(size,3,3))
        p = np.reshape(p,(size,3,3))
    if R.ndim == 2:
        R = np.reshape(R, (1,3,3))
        p = np.reshape(p, (1,3,3))
    observation_times = np.array(observation_times)
    # dividing observation times into set of three
    observation_times = np.reshape(observation_times, (size,3))

```

Fig. 7. This figure shows how data type and dimensional consistency challenge was addressed in the Python implementation. NumPy arrays played an important handling multiple observation sets simultaneously, ensuring proper reshaping and alignment of the data. The Python library and this design choice simplified debugging and ensured that each dataset could be processed accurately, regardless of its dimensional structure.

V. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

Through this project, we first developed a mathematical and physical understanding of Gauss’s method, including its inherent limitations in both formulation and application. We then examined the original Fortran implementation of the method, performing a direct translation of the code into Python. This translation process deepened our understanding of Fortran’s structure and functionality, while also allowing us to compare its computational approach to that of Python. Finally, we designed and implemented an enhanced Python version of Gauss’s method. This new implementation is capable of efficiently processing multiple sets of observational data, while also incorporating modern programming practices that improve both readability and performance. By combining our mathematical insight with computational refinement, we were able to connect the theoretical and practical aspects of orbital determination.

Overall, this project resulted in a robust and scalable Python implementation of Gauss’s Method capable of handling multiple observational datasets simultaneously. Looking forward, future work will involve a systematic comparison between the Fortran and Python outputs coming from the same database, to further validate and refine the new implementation. This comparison will also allow us to quantify any computational or numerical differences between the two languages. With this Python version, we can begin to explore more advanced and conceptual questions, not only determining what the estimated orbital trajectory is, but also understanding why the method yields that particular estimate. Future analyses may include studying how the choice of three observations affects orbital accuracy, how observation time intervals influence the results, and whether an optimal time spacing exists for minimizing error and creating the best trajectory estimate.

Additionally, synthetic uncertainties can be introduced into the data to assess how measurement errors propagate through the method. By combining theoretical understanding, computational development, and systematic analysis, this work provides a strong foundation for further exploration of the Gauss’s method for orbital determination methods it’s modern computational applications.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to Dr. Payne for his invaluable guidance throughout this project and for helping me develop a deeper understanding of the material and research process. I would also like to thank Dr. Spoto from the Center for Astrophysics for her insightful ideas, thoughtful feedback, and continued support in shaping this work.

I am deeply grateful to my advisors at Bridgewater State University, Dr. Winters and Dr. Gross, for their constant support, time, and dedication in mentoring me through this research, as well as for their thoughtful feedback on this paper and its revisions.

REFERENCES

- [1] Wikipedia contributors. Carl friedrich gauss. https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Carl_friedrich_Gauss&oldid=1314864335, 2010. Accessed : 2025 – 09 – 21.
- [2] Wikipedia contributors. Gauss’s method. <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Gauss> Accessed: 2025-05-06.
- [3] Giovanni F. Gronchi. Classical and modern orbit determination for asteroids. *proceedings international astronomical unios*, (196):1–11, 2004.
- [4] Dmitry Savransky. 4 - 1 - gauss’s method. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kIw2yDNpqQ>, May 2022.

Milagros Tamara Giraldo is a senior at Bridgewater State University (BSU) (United States) pursuing a double bachelor’s degree in computer science and physics with a concentration in Astrophysics, along with a minor in Mathematics and an Undergraduate Certificate in Data Science. She is part of the BSU Honors Program and a member of the Upsilon Pi

Epsilon Honors Society. Since the summer of 2024, Milagros has been interning at the Center for Astrophysics — Harvard & Smithsonian, where she continues to strengthen her computational and research skills while deepening her understanding of orbital mechanics and astrophysical systems. After graduation in May 2026, she intends to pursue a Ph.D. in physics to further expand her knowledge about the physical universe. Her academic interests center on the intersection of computation, mathematics, astrophysics and theoretical physics.